

Q band waveguide resonant cavity with high quality factor

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Abstract — In this paper, a study related to the unloaded quality factor Q_0 of a resonant cavity using rectangular waveguide technology is described. The resonator operates at Q band (33 - 50 GHz) with a central frequency of 41,5 GHz, with two ports. Simulations are done using Ansys HFSS. The results obtained with copper show a high unload quality factor Q_0 .

I. INTRODUCTION

Waveguide resonant cavities are key components in varieties of passive devices for communication systems, including radio transmission, cellular radio, satellite communication systems, and broadband wireless communications. In this paper, a rectangular waveguide cavity resonator is described. The resonators will be used to design stopband filters for instantaneous frequency measurement receiver (IFM) implementations. Essential components of IFM receivers are the frequency discriminators. They are generally composed of interferometers based on delay lines. Usually these devices use planar technology [1]. This work is the first design stage to implement a new IFM architecture based on resonant cavities made using waveguides, where stopband filters will replace the delay line based interferometers [2-4]. For the IFM implementation, the filters used are made with planar technology, generally with microstrip transmission lines [5]. The resonator designed can be fabricated with a high quality factor. Filter based IFM can improve delay line implementations, since the delay lines present difficulty to generate uniform resolutions and may present ambiguities in the results. Rectangular waveguides have low losses and high quality factor and are efficient structures for communication systems and radar, with high power handling. With the rapid development of wireless communications, the demand for microwave circuits of compact size, high performance and low cost is a constant challenge. The Q band is mainly used for satellite communications, remote sensing, terrestrial microwave communications and radio astronomy studies. It is currently being explored for future commercial telecommunications programs in the space industry [6]. This fact is opening up a

huge potential for a wide range of new microwave components for military and commercial applications, just as it happened two decades ago with the Ka band. Some of the challenges of circuit design in the Q band are cost and the new technology that must be developed to create reliable circuits. The resonator in this paper will be implemented with 3D printing technology and metalized using electroless plating to obtain a component of low weight and low cost.

II. DESIGN

For the resonator design, standard flange dimensions of waveguide WR22 are used, namely $a=5.68$ mm, $b=2.84$ mm (see Fig.1).

Fig 1:3D view of the proposed resonator with physical dimensions

When a waveguide section is short circuited at both ends, it exhibits resonant properties at frequencies when the length is $\lambda/2$ or a multiple of $\lambda/2$. To calculate c , we consider the dominant mode $TE_{1,0}$. Multiple modes of operation are possible. Normally only low order modes are of interest to avoid dispersion. Using the expression in eq.1 the resonant frequency for the $TE_{1,0}$ mode

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is calculated. The value of λ is 7,22 mm, thus $\lambda/2$ is 3,61 mm, corresponding to dimension of c (see Fig.1).

$$f_{c,TE}^{TE} = c \sqrt{\left(\frac{m}{2a}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{n}{2b}\right)^2} \quad \text{eq.1}$$

The physical dimensions of the weak coupling iris between the resonator and the two ports was set $t=0.4$ mm (t corresponds to the iris wall thickness), $a=2.50$ mm and $b=2.84$ mm. Fig.2 shows a view of the resonator with the standard flanges.

Fig 2: 3D view of the resonator with standard waveguide flanges

III. SIMULATION

Simulation results are obtained using the high frequency FEM simulation software (Ansys HFSS).

The unloaded quality factor is estimated when parameter S_{21} is, at least, at the attenuation point of -20 dB or more, to achieve a weak coupling and neglect the external quality factor. Fig 3 shows the response of the copper resonator. The Q band resonator is weakly coupled with the input and output ports symmetrically. The quality factor Q is the relation between the center frequency of the filter and the 3 dB bandwidth.

Fig 3. Simulation of the proposed copper resonator

IV. RESULTS

Table 1 shows the simulation results of the resonator. Resonance frequency is 41.599 GHz and the 3 dB bandwidth is 12 MHz. The quality factor of the simulated copper resonator is 3495. The results obtained demonstrate a high quality factor suitable for the design of high performance filters.

Table 1: proposed resonator simulated results

Resonance frequency f_0	41,599 GHz
Lower cutting frequency f_l	41,593 GHz
Superior cutting frequency f_2	41,605 GHz
Bandwidth (3dB)	12 MHz
Q_0 Copper structure	3495

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, a rectangular waveguide resonator simulated with Ansys HFSS with high unloaded quality Q_0 is described. The high Q_0 obtained indicates that the proposed resonator can be used to make high performance filters for IFM receivers [7]. The proposed resonator with high quality factor can be used to achieve selective filters for the detection of signals with low insertion losses. The high performance filters will serve to eliminate ambiguities between results, a fact commonly observed with other designs such as those implemented with delay lines in microstrip technology [2-4].

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